

FIELD PERFORMANCE OF SEED YAM (*Dioscorea rotundata* Poir) PRODUCED USING LEAF-BUD CUTTINGS AND HYDROPONIC SUBSTRATES

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ABSTRACT

Yam (Dioscorea spp.) is a staple crop in West Africa, yet high seed yam costs, low multiplication rates, and disease susceptibility in traditional propagation methods hinder its productivity. This study evaluated the field performance of Asiedu and Kpamyio seed yams produced from leaf-bud cuttings (LBCs) grown in hydroponic substrates in a screenhouse. The hydroponics substrates were cocopeat (COP), carbonised rice husk (CRH), fermented rice husk (FRH), sandponics (RSD), and topsoil (TPS) as a control. A 2×5 factorial experiment arranged in a Randomised Complete Block Design (RCBD) with three replications was conducted at IITA Abuja during the 2021 and 2022 cropping seasons. Growth and yield parameters, including % establishment, days to 50% establishment, vine length, leaf area index, chlorophyll content, tuber yield, and sett multiplication ratio (SMR), were collected and analysed. Results showed a per cent field establishment of over 90.0% for both varieties. Kpamyio significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) outperformed Asiedu in most vegetative traits measured, and Kpamyio's yield (25.3 t/ha) was 17.7% more than that of Asiedu (21.5 t/ha). FRH and COP significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) improved all vegetative and yield traits. FRH consistently supported superior growth, yielding up to 28.7 t/ha for Kpamyio. Fresh tuber yield positively correlated with vegetative parameters, showing the importance of early growth and development. Although TPS had lower yields, it recorded the highest SMR (62.9). Dry matter content was higher in Asiedu (31.6%) than in Kpamyio (30.4%). The findings prove that seed yams produced from LBCs and hydroponics, especially in FRH, are good planting materials and capable of producing high yields.

Keywords: Seed yam, hydroponics, substrates, leaf-bud cuttings.

INTRODUCTION

Yams (*Dioscorea spp.*) are a staple crop in tropical regions and are important for nutrition, food security, and sociocultural traditions, especially in West Africa (González & José, 2019). Of the 600 *Dioscorea* species known to humans, about

six, including white yam, are commercially important in West Africa for food, medicine, and revenue creation (Obidiegwu *et al.*, 2020; Verter & Bečvářová, 2015). In 2022, 74.8 million tons of yams were produced worldwide, with Nigeria accounting for 50.1 million tons, or 66.9% of the total

production (FAO, 2024). Demand with produce its significant role in global food security, hydroponic systems such as low rates of numerous advantages, such as low rates of numerous materials and to improve the between seed and food production as planted seed for bigger seeds or 30% of their production. This study followed in planting season (higher yield and yield 2020) performance of seed yam produced from limitations of crop productivity and to overcome Asiedu and Kp. Traditional yam propagation methods such as whole tubers or screen sets, which are mostly, have a poor ratio of multiplication (1:4 to 1:10), and are vulnerable to soil-borne infections and

nematodes, among other pests and diseases (Morse, 2022). A new way of propagating seed yam that avoids the drawbacks of conventional tuber-based techniques of yam production is the use of leaf-bud cuttings (LBCs). Leaf-bud cuttings present a viable substitute since they allow for quick multiplication of seeds up to 1:300 in aeroponics and hydroponics systems, yielding pest-free, high-quality seed yam that can be used locally or exchanged for germplasm was recorded from March to October, internationally (Maroya *et al.*, 2014). To produce seed yam, LBCs are planted in hydroponic substrates such as cocopeat, average minimum air temperatures for 2021 carbonised rice husk, fermented rice husk, and sandponics (Aighewi *et al.*, 2025) in the screen house. This ensures increased nutrient availability, water retention, and aeration and lowers the danger of soil-borne diseases, thus producing high-quality seed yams (Djaingsastro *et al.*, 2021). This technique improves the efficiency of seed yam production and lessens dependency on tubers; whole tubers can be saved for food or the market by planting, thus addressing the lack of high-quality seed yams noted in West Africa.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The field experiment was carried out at the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA) research farm in Abuja, Nigeria, during the 2021 and 2022 cropping seasons. The site is situated in Nigeria's "Yam Belt" at coordinates 9.164030°N, 7.346236°E, and an altitude of 424 meters above sea level. The soil is sandy loamy Alfisol (Fairhurst *et al.*, 2012) in texture and slightly acidic with a pH range of 6.3–6.4. The climate is tropical, and in 2021, rainfall totalling 1004.2 mm. In 2022, the rainfall occurred from February to November, with a cumulative amount of 1173.5 mm. The average minimum air temperatures for 2021 and 2022 were 21.0 °C and 21.4 C, respectively, while the average maximum temperatures were 32.1 °C and 32.3 C, respectively (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: Metrological data for rainfall and temperature during the cropping seasons from 2021 to 2022 at the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture Station, Abuja, Nigeria.

Planting materials used were the seed yam of the two improved varieties, Asiedu and Kpamyo, that were produced by planting leaf-bud cuttings (LBCs) in different substrates Cocopeat (COP), carbonised rice husk (CRH), fermented rice husk (FRH), sandponics (RSD), and topsoil (TPS), during the 2020 and 2021 cropping seasons. These seeds were relatively small in size, with a mean weight of 24.0 g and 30 g for Asiedu and Kpamyo planted, respectively. The field was ploughed, harrowed, and cleared using a tractor, with ridges spaced 100 cm apart. Seed yams were treated before planting to guard against pest damage and rot. This was done by soaking the seeds in a solution comprising insecticide (cypermethrin 40 EC, 40 mL/L) and a fungicide (mancozeb 80% WP, 10 g/L) for 10 minutes (Aighewi *et al.*, 2014). To allow curing before planting, treated

tubers were allowed to air dry in the shade for a full day. Seed yams were planted on top of the ridges on June 29, 2021, and June 27, 2022, at a depth of around 7 cm. The plant density was 33,333 plants/ha, with planting spacing of 30 cm within rows and 1 m between rows. There were 40 plants in each plot. Three replications and a 2 x 5 factorial were used to set up the experiment in a Randomised Complete Block Design (RCBD). There were 30 plots overall, with 10 experimental units in each replication. There was a 1 m alley between plots and a 2 m alley between duplicates, and each plot was 4 x 2 m (8 m²). The experiment was laid out in a 2 x 5 factorial fitted into a Randomised Complete Block Design (RCBD) with three replications. Each replicate contained 10 experimental units, totalling 30 plots. Each plot measured 4x2 m (8 m²), with a 1 m alley between plots and

a 2 m alley between replicates. The total experimental area was 20 m × 14 m, accommodating a plant population of 1,200 stands.

Three days after planting, pre-emergence herbicides (Premextra (290 g/L S-Metolachlor, 370 g/L Atrazine) at 3.2 kg/ha and post-emergence herbicide (200 g/L Paraquat) at 1.0 kg/ha were applied using a Knapsack sprayer. The grids were then earthed up to retain their structure and set multiplication ratio (SMR) was calculated as the ratio of the total weight of harvested tubers to the weight of planted material using the trellis method at 8 WAP. This material involves tying ropes between bamboo poles at each ridge's end. To improve the availability of nutrients, 400 kg/ha of NPK 15:15:15 fertiliser was spread in bands on either side of the ridges at 8 WAP (Akpan *et al.*, 2021).

Data Collection: Plant establishment percentage was recorded at 8 weeks after planting (WAP). Days to 50% assess the establishment were assessed by counting the number of sprouted tubers every four days until 50% of tubers were tubers had sprouted. At 12 WAP, 10 plants were standardised (6H) and a crop cut on 60 cm height (analysis was conducted to evaluate relationships between agronomic parameters).

RESULTS
 The analysis of variance shows that, which on the whole achieved 92.2% and 90.5% field establishment (Fig. 1) and they were not significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$) as shown in Table 1. Among the substrates used to produce the seed yam, CRH exhibited the highest establishment rate at 94.75%, and its establishment was not significantly different from CRH and FRH but it significantly ($p < 0.05$) surpassed TPS selected and tagged plants between the establishment and recording the displayed SPAD value after three seconds. When plants reached senescence at 22 WAP, consistent across years. Harvesting was conducted on December 3,

2021, and December 1, 2022. Fresh tuber yield (t/ha) was determined by weighing tubers harvested from the net plot using a digital electronic scale (SF-400), mean

tuber weight (g) and harvest index (HI) were also recorded. The dry matter (%) content was determined by drying a 20 g

sample and tuber emergence characteristics at 8 WAP (Fig. 2) (kg/ha) were applied using a Knapsack sprayer. The grids were then earthed up to retain their structure and set multiplication ratio (SMR) was calculated as the ratio of the total weight of harvested tubers to the weight of planted material using the equation below:

$$SMR = \frac{\text{Weight of harvested tubers}}{\text{Weight of the planted material}}$$

Data Analysis: Data were analysed using the ‘agricolae’ package in the R Statistical Programme (version 4.5.0). Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed to assess the treatment effects, with means

separated using the Least Significant Difference (LSD) test at $p \leq 0.05$. Where Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT) and

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Fig 2: A = Planting of seed yam produced from different substrates; B = Growing yam plants in the field

It was observed that both varieties achieved days to 50% establishment at 21.4 and 22.2 days for Asiedu and Kpamyo, respectively. However, substrate had a significant influence on this attribute, with seed yam grown using FRH being the fastest to reach day to 50% establishment at 19.6 days, significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) reducing the time by 15.2% when compared to TPS (23.08 days). RSD was the slowest at 25.67 days; its sprouting was delayed for an extra 6.1 days when compared to FRH. Kpamyo's vine length (326.48 cm) was 14.0% longer than Asiedu's (286.31 cm), and its number of leaves (203.26) was 28.0% higher than

Asiedu's (158.76); both were significantly different. FRH supported the longest vines 337.59 cm and the most leaves 198.71, which were significantly different from TPS's vine length (265.9 cm) and number of leaves (166.8). Leaf Area Index (LAI) was highest in FRH (5.9), 51.3% greater than TPS (3.9), and they were significantly different. Irrespective of variety, Chlorophyll content (SPAD) recorded in all substrates was above 30; however, FRH had the highest SPAD value of 34.1, and it was significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) different from RSD and TPS.

Table 1: The vegetative characteristics of seed yam produced from hydroponic substrates and leaf-bud cuttings as evaluated in the field during the 2021 and 2022 cropping seasons

Factors	% Establishment (8WAP)	Days to 50% establishment	Length (cm) of vine – 12 WAP	Number of leaves – 12 WAP	Leaf Area Index – 12 WAP	Chlorophyll Content – 12 WAP
Variety						
Asiedu	90.5a	21.4a	286.3b	158.8b	4.8a	31.8b
Kpamyo	92.2a	22.2a	326.5a	203.3a	4.9a	33.1a
LSD _(0.05)	3.17	1.35	20.63	15.58	0.40	1.35

Substrates						
COP	94.8a	20.0c	297.4bc	179.4ab	5.4ab	33.2ab
CRH	90.9abc	20.6c	323.5ab	183.5ab	4.9bc	33.5a
FRH	94.1ab	19.6c	337.6a	198.7a	5.9a	34.1a
RSD	89.5bc	25.67a	307.6ab	176.6ab	4.4cd	31.1bc
TPS	87.5c	23.1b	265.9c	166.8b	3.9d	30.5c
LSD (0.05)	5.01	2.13	32.61	24.63	0.64	2.13
Year						
2020	90.2a	22.6a	295.4b	173.3a	4.8a	32.6a
2021	92.5a	21.0b	317.4a	188.7a	4.9a	32.4a
LSD (0.05)	3.17	1.35	20.63	15.58	0.40	1.35

Means followed by the same letter(s) in a column of treatments are not significantly different at $p = 0.05$ using LSD. WAP = Weeks after planting. COP = Cocopeat, CRH = Carbonised rice husk, FRH = Fermented rice husk, RSD = Sandponics, TPS = Topsoil.

Fresh tuber yield was significantly higher for Kpamyo at 25.3 t/ha compared to Asiedu's 21.49 t/ha, a 17.6% yield increase reflecting Kpamyo's superior yield potential (Table 2). Among substrates, FRH multiplication ratio (SMR) was yielded the highest at 27.0 t/ha, and it was not significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$) from the yield obtained from other substrates except for TPS (16.4 t/ha), which had a 35.2% decrease in yield when compared to FRH. Yield in 2021 (24.75 t/ha) was significantly higher than in 2020 (22.01 t/ha) by 12.4%. Mean tuber weight was not significantly different was recorded among substrates; it was significantly different from CRH (66.0g) ($p \leq 0.05$). FRH produced the heaviest tubers at 440.4 g, significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) outperforming TPS (289.6 g) by 51.9%.

The number of tubers per hectare was significantly higher for Kpamyo (63,725) than for Asiedu (57,158) by 11.5%, with no significant substrate differences. Sett multiplication ratio (SMR) was significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) highest in TPS (57.0), 114.3% greater than FRH (26.6). Per cent dry matter was slightly higher in Asiedu (31.64%) than in Kpamyo (30.42%); however, no substrate differences were recorded for dry matter. Harvest index (HI) for both varieties was statistically at par, although a significant difference was recorded among substrates; it was highest in RSD (72.0) and it was significantly different from CRH (66.0) ($p \leq 0.05$), indicating efficient biomass partitioning.

Table 2: The yield attributes of seed yam produced from hydroponic substrates and leaf-bud cuttings as evaluated in the field during the 2021 and 2022 cropping seasons

Factors	Fresh tuber yield (t/ha)	Mean weight (g)/tuber	Number of tubers/Ha	Sett multiplication ratio	% Dry matter	Harvest Index
Variety						
Asiedu	21.5b	376.6a	57158.0b	32.0a	31.6a	66.0a
Kpamyo	25.3a	401.6a	63725.0a	31.3a	30.4b	68.7a
LSD (0.05)	2.43	50.17	3863.71	7.25	0.97	3.28

Substrates						
COP	25.6a	407.8a	62552.0a	25.6b	30.4a	68.9ab
CRH	24.8a	406.6a	61177.0a	24.6b	30.9a	66.3b
FRH	27.0a	440.4a	61875.0a	26.6b	31.8a	69.2ab
RSD	23.2a	401.1a	58739.0a	24.5b	30.4a	72.0a
TPS	16.47b	289.6b	57864.0a	57.0a	31.6a	60.3c
LSD (0.05)	3.85	79.32	6109.06	11.47	1.53	5.19
Yea						
r	22.0b	383.8a	56875.0b	28.7a	31.2a	66.6a
2020	24.8a	394.4a	64008.0a	34.5a	30.87a	68.1a
2021 (0.05)	2.43	50.17	3863.71	7.25	0.97	3.28

LSD means followed by the same letter(s) in a column of treatments are not significantly different at $p = 0.05$ using LSD. COP = Cocopeat, CRH = Carbonised rice husk, FRH = Fermented rice husk, RSD = Sandponics, TPS = Topsoil.

The interaction between yam varieties and substrates on the growth and yield of seed yam derived from LBCs was significant, and it influenced most vegetative parameters measured, as shown in Table 3. Days to 50% establishment showed a significant ($p \leq 0.05$) interactions with Kpamyo seed yam produced using COP and FRH achieved the fastest sprouting at 17.5 days each, a 26.2% increase in the rate of sprouting than Kpamyo seed yam produced using TPS (23.7 days), which was significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) slower. Faster sprouting, particularly in COP and FRH for Kpamyo, likely enhanced early vegetative growth, contributing to higher fresh tuber yields by extending the period for biomass accumulation. Kpamyo seeds produced from FRH had the longest vines at 364.4 cm, followed by Kpamyo in CRH (344.3), and the least Asiedu in TSP with a vine length of 249.5 cm. Irrespective of the substrate, the Kpamyo variety had more leaves than the Asiedu variety. The highest number of leaves, 223.8, was recorded for Kpamyo in FRH, and it was significantly different from Asiedu seeds yam obtained from all substrates used for the seed production. Kpamyo in CRH (344.3 cm, 208.78 leaves) and COP (324.47 cm, 189.24 leaves) also outperformed TPS, with increases of 22.0% and 14.0% in vine length and 14.2% and 3.5% in leaf number, respectively. Leaf Area Index (LAI) was significantly highest for Kpamyo in FRH at 6.2 and the least in Kpamyo in TPS, with an LAI value of 3.7. The range of LAI values for Asiedu is 4.1 to 5.6, while Kpamyo was 3.7 to 6.2.

Table 3: The interaction between hydroponic substrates and yam varieties on the vegetative parameters of seed yam during the 2021 and 2022 cropping seasons.

Variety	Substrate	Daysto50%	Lengthofvine– 12WAP	Numberof leaves_ 12WAP	LeafArea Index– 12WAP
Asiedu	COP	22.5b	270.3de	169.6cd	5.2abc
	CRH	17.8c	302.7bcd	158.3cd	4.8bcd
	FRH	21.7b	310.8bcd	173.6bcd	5.6ab
	RSD	22.3b	298.3bcde	141.6d	4.5cde
	TPS	22.5b	249.5e	150.8cd	4.1de
Kpamyo	COP	17.5c	324.5abc	189.2abc	5.6ab
	CRH	23.3b	344.3ab	208.8ab	4.9bcd
	FRH	17.5c	364.4a	223.8a	6.2a
	RSD	29.0a	316.9abcd	211.6ab	4.2de
	TPS	23.7b	282.3cde	182.9bc	3.7e
SE±		1.06	16.14	12.19	0.32

Means followed by the same letter(s) in a column of treatments are not significantly different using DMRT at $p = 0.05$., SE = Standard error, WAP = weeks after planting. COP = Cocopeat, CRH = Carbonised rice husk, FRH = Fermented rice husk, RSD = Sandponics, TPS = Topsoil.

Table 4 shows how yam varieties and hydroponic substrates interacted to affect seed yam yield and yield metrics in the 2021 and 2022 cropping seasons. Kpamyo seeds yam produced using FRH substrate produced the highest fresh tuber yield at 28.7 t/ha, and it was not significantly different from the fresh tuber yield obtained from Kpamyo in COP (28.4 t/ha), CRH (27.3 t/ha) and RSD (23.8 t/ha), except for Kpamyo in TPS (18.2 t/ha). A 57.7% increase was recorded when Kpamyo TPS was compared with Kpamyo in FRH. Asiedu in FRH yielded 25.2 t/ha, and it was not significantly different from others except for Asiedu in TPS (22.52 t/ha). Mean tuber weight for Kpamyo in FRH (527.1 g) was highest for Kpamyo in FRH (527.1 g), followed by Asiedu in RSD (72.2); they were not significantly different from varieties except for Asiedu in TSP (58.7) and Kpamyo in TPS (66.0) tubers. Kpamyo in FRH produced the biggest tubers with a mean weight of 449.2 g, and it was not significantly different from others, except for Kpamyo in TPS (313.7 g) and Asiedu in TPS (265.4 g). Larger tuber weights in FRH and COP for both varieties directly contributed to higher fresh tuber yields by increasing individual tuber contributions. The number of tubers per hectare was highest for Kpamyo in CRH (67,729.0) and least for Asiedu in TPS (55,833.0). Sett multiplication ratio (SMR) was highest for Asiedu in TPS (62.9) and significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$) from others, except for Kpamyo in TPS (51.08); however, the lowest SMR was obtained in Asiedu RSD (23.2). Per cent dry matter was highest for Asiedu in TPS (32.4%) and FRH (31.7%), significantly different from others except for Kpamyo in RSD (28.7%). Harvest Index (HI) was highest for Kpamyo in FRH (72.7%), followed by Asiedu in RSD (72.2); they were not significantly different from varieties except for Asiedu in TSP (58.7) and Kpamyo in TPS (66.0) tubers. Kpamyo in FRH produced the biggest tubers with a mean weight of 449.2 g, and it was not significantly different from others, except for Kpamyo in TPS (313.7 g) and Asiedu in TPS (265.4 g).

Table 4: The interaction between hydroponic substrates and yam varieties on the yield and yield parameters of seed yam during the 2021 and 2022 cropping seasons.

Variety	Substrate	Fresh tuber yield (t/ha)	Mean weight (g)/tuber	Number of tubers/ha	Sett multiplication ratio	%Dry matter	Harvest Index
Asiedu	COP	22.7abc	385.5ab	58854.0abc	23.8b	30.8ab	66.8ab
	CRH	22.2bc	407.0ab	54625.0c	25.0b	31.1ab	66.5ab
	FRH	25.2ab	431.6ab	59208.0abc	24.9b	31.7a	65.7ab
	RSD	22.5abc	393.7ab	57270.0bc	23.2b	32.2a	72.2a
	TPS	14.8d	265.4c	55833.0c	62.9a	32.4a	58.7b
Kpamyo	COP	28.4ab	430.1ab	66250.0ab	27.3b	30.0ab	70.7a
	CRH	27.3ab	406.2ab	67729.0a	24.2b	30.8ab	66.2ab
	FRH	28.7a	449.2a	64541.0abc	28.1b	31.8a	72.7a
	RSD	23.8abc	408.5ab	60208.0abc	25.9b	28.7b	71.8a
	TPS	18.2cd	313.7bc	59895.0abc	51.1a	30.8ab	62.0b
SE±		1.90	39.25	3022.68	5.68	0.76	2.57

Means followed by the same letter(s) in a column of treatments are not significantly different using DMRT at $p = 0.05$, SE = Standard error, ha = hectare. COP = Cocopeat, CRH = Carbonised rice husk, FRH = Fermented rice husk, RSD = Sandponics, TPS = Topsoil.

The correlation analysis revealed positive relationships between fresh tuber yield and vegetative traits, as shown in Table 5. The correlation coefficient between fresh tuber yield and vine length was $r = 0.62^*$, and number of leaves ($r = 0.52^*$), LAI ($r = 0.48^{**}$), and chlorophyll content ($r = 0.34^{**}$), all significant at $p \leq 0.05$, indicating that vigorous vegetative growth enhanced yield. Days to 50% establishment showed a non-significant negative correlation ($r = -0.17$), suggesting that although faster sprouting and growth supported more yield, it did not significantly boost the yield of the seed yam planted.

Table 5: Matrix correlation coefficient between the yield of seed yam produced from hydroponic substrates and LBCs and vegetative parameters in the 2021 and 2022 rainy seasons at Abuja.

	Fresh tuber yield(t/ha)	% Establishment	Days to 50% establishment	Vine length	No. leaves	LAI	SPAD	HI
Yield (t/ha)	1							
% Establishment	0.38**	1						
Days to 50% establishment	-0.17	-0.03	1					
Vine length	0.62*	0.24	-0.21	1				
No. leaves	0.52*	0.29*	-0.05	0.29*	1			
LAI	0.48**	0.34**	-0.45**	0.30*	0.37*	1		
SPAD	0.34**	0.23	-0.32*	0.25	0.11	0.53**	1	
HI	0.76**	0.24	-0.05	0.09	0.25	0.25	0.11	1

Pearson bivariate correlation (2-tailed), * = Correlation is significant at $p = 0.05$. Yield (t/ha) = fresh tuber yield (t/ha), % stand = per cent plant stand, Establishment (50%) = Days to 50% establishment, Vine length (cm), No. leaves = Number of leaves, LAI = Leaf area index, SPAD = Chlorophyll content, HI = Harvest Index.

1. DISCUSSION

Vegetative attributes of seed yam produced from LBCs and hydroponics as evaluated in the field.

Well-preserved seed tubers usually develop buds at the proximal end at the break of dormancy; some cultivars produce a single bud, while others may produce several buds (Elsie Hamadina, 2011). These tubers sprout quickly and thrive when planted in

In this fertile soil under ideal conditions, more than 90% of the high-quality seed yams planted successfully sprouted. These results were corroborated by Aighewi *et al.*, (2020), who observed 92–96% survival for 45 g whole-seed yams at 12 WAP. The absence of noticeable variations between varieties for field establishment suggests that both are field-adapted varieties.

With days to 50% establishment taking place after 21.4 days for Asiedu and 22.2 days for Kpamyo, the seed yams established. Depending on the type of hydroponic substrate, agronomic characteristics such as the number of leaves, vine length (cm), leaf area index (LAI), and chlorophyll content varied significantly.

The field performance of seed yam produced using TPS was less than that of seed yam produced using COP, CRH, and Stronger field performance was made possible by the superior vegetative development that these hydroponic substrates promoted.

The longer vines had more branches and leaves, which increased their LAI. This finding agrees with Akinbo *et al.*, (2021), who found that vine length, number of leaves, and leaf area index significantly increased as fertiliser application increased. The increased LAI in seed yam produced using FRH and COP increased

photosynthetic efficiency, which is associated with better light capture during early growth (Melteras *et al.*, 2008). While SPAD levels of chlorophyll were moderate, notable substrate-driven differences showed improved uptake of nitrogen, which is essential for biomass and photosynthesis (Pepe, 2020). The improved vegetative traits in FRH, CRH, and COP substrates supported increased production of photosynthate, which increased tuber bulking and fresh tuber yield through improved source capacity.

Yield and yield components of seed yam produced from LBCs and hydroponics as evaluated in the field.

Fresh yam tubers are essential for home consumption, industrial use, and farmers' income because they are both the main harvest and the planting material for subsequent crops (Maroya *et al.*, 2022). In this study, Nigeria's average yam landrace yield of 9 t/ha was greatly exceeded by Asiedu's yield of 21.8 t/ha and Kpamyo's output of 25.3 t/ha (FAOSTAT, 2024). This resulted in 168.8% and 16.3% yield increases for Asiedu and Kpamyo when compared to average yields from farmers' fields. Hence, using improved seed yams for propagation is essential to maximising yields per unit area (Corner *et al.*, 2025). According to Seedportal (2025), Kpamyo's yield for ware yam production was close to its potential of 30 t/ha. Among the hydroponics substrates used to produce the seed yam, FRH, CRH, and COP consistently outperformed TPS because they promoted robust vine and leaf growth, which increased the amount of assimilate produced for tuber development (Balogun *et al.*, 2021). From the correlation analysis, fresh tuber

yield was strongly positively correlated with vine length, number of leaves, and leaf area index, highlighting the significance of robust vegetative development in increasing seed yam production (Ekwere *et al.*, 2023). According to Kleih *et al.*, (2012), a farmer can get up to 6,000–10,000 plant stands per hectare in the traditional system of yam cultivation, where seeds are planted in mounds. However, we achieved a population density of 33,333 plants per hectare by planting on ridges at a spacing of 30 cm by 100 cm; this resulted in 57,158 tubers for Asiedu and 63,725 for Kpamyo per hectare. Additionally, ridges are better than mounds in terms of fertiliser efficiency (Ennin *et al.*, 2009). Better rainfall in 2021 aided fertiliser uptake and raised yields by 12.7% over 2020. Notwithstanding the high fresh tuber yield, previous studies on the effect of set size on yam yield have shown the positive relationship between the size of sets planted and the weight of fresh tubers harvested (Emokaro & Law-Ogbomo, 2008). However, the increase in sett size planted was not directly proportional to the increase in the fresh tuber yield, as doubling the size of seed planted from about 125 g to 250 g only increased tuber yield by 20%. On the other hand, 30% SMR is higher for high tuber yields. smaller setts, since the additional yield from

larger setts is usually smaller than the additional weight of the planting material. In the quest to produce more yam, farmers plant a large seed, which reduces the quantity of tubers available for food. In this study, the tubers were fairly uniform, having mean weights per tuber of 376.6 g for Asiedu and 401.6 g for Kpamyo. This is in line with the findings of Aighewi *et al.*, (2020); she observed that the mean weight per tuber from 45 g of whole sett was 900 g. The observed dry matter content of Asiedu was 29.1% less than the dry matter content documented in Seedportal (2025); however, it showed a greater dry matter content than Kpamyo.

CONCLUSION

These results show the potential of seed yams derived LBCs and hydroponics as a viable, scalable approach to addressing seed yam scarcity and enhancing yam productivity in West Africa. This study shows that seed yams produced from leaf-bud cuttings using hydroponic substrates, particularly fermented rice husk (FRH), perform well under field conditions. The improved yam varieties, Asiedu and Kpamyo, showed high establishment rates and strong vegetative growth, resulting in

On the other hand, 30% SMR is higher for high tuber yields.

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